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Research Article

**DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ETHOSOME DRUG
DELIVERY SYSTEM CONTAINING ISRADIPINE FOR
TOPICAL APPLICATION****Dibyalochan Mohanty¹, Manoranjan Sahu, Rakesh Kumar Jat**Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University, Institute of Pharmacy, Jhunjhunu-333001,
Rajasthan, India.**Abstract:**

The increasing demand for efficient administration and delivery of Pharmaceutical dosage forms possessing the attributes namely minimum side effects, improved patient compliance has resulted in the formulation of novel drug delivery system. The revolutionary technology of drug delivery is off late being focused on the transdermal route in contrast to the conventional oral route. More over the bioavailability is poor and the onset of action is slow for most of the drugs, which are sparingly suitable in water. Ethosomes are very effective since they enhance the penetration of drugs via skin to several times whose compound to the simple creams, elixirs and liposomal carriers. Hence, there is an absolute necessity to formulate Isradipine as Ethosomes in order to increase the penetration of the drug through the skin. This would avoid the inherent defects of Isradipine administered via oral route. Preparation of Isradipine Ethosomes involves the procedure as described. 20-40% of Ethanol, 10% of propylene glycol, 2-5% of phospholipids, 0-0.05g of cholesterol and an aqueous part of 100% w/w, were taken At room temperature 0.025g of Isradipine was added to ethanol in a covered vessel along with propylene glycol and dissolved by vigorous stirring. In a separate vessel, the mixture was heated to 30^oc and this was added to the mixture in the centre of the vessel by stirring at 700 rpm for 5 min in a covered vessel. Then by Sonication method the vesicle size of Isradipine Ethosomes was reduced to the desirable extent and the formulation was kept under refrigeration. The same procedure was followed for the preparation of Unsonicated Ethosomes, except that they were not sonicated. Isradipine Liposome's were also prepared. They were prepared by the Cast Film method. The prepared formulations are tested for various physiochemical parameters and positive results are obtained and the best/optimized formulations are selected by the better drug release from the formulations prepared. Optimized formulations are subjected to in vivo studies and observed for in vivo blood pressure response in the BP induced animals and positive results are observed in the given time periods.

Key words: Isradipine, Ethosomes, Sonicator

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INTRODUCTION:

For a long time treatment of intense sicknesses or endless ailments have been generally proficient by conveyance of medications to patients utilizing different pharmaceutical measurements frames including tablets, containers, suppositories, creams, balms, fluids, pressurized canned products & injectables¹. Indeed, even today these customary measurements shapes are the essential pharmaceutical vehicles regularly found in the medicine & over the counter medication advertise. The oral customary kinds of medication conveyance frameworks are known to give an incite arrival of the medication². Along these lines to accomplish & also to keep up the medication fixation inside the restoratively successful range required for treatment, it is regularly important to take this sort of medication conveyance framework a few times each day. This outcomes in a critical variance in medicate levels frequently with a sub-helpful as well as harmful levels & wastage of medication. As of late a few specialized headways have brought about the advancement of new frameworks of medication conveyance equipped for controlling the rate of medication conveyance, supporting the span of remedial movement & focusing on the conveyance of medication to a tissue. The term controlled discharge suggests a framework that gives ceaseless conveyance of the medication for a foreordained period with unsurprising & reproducible energy & a known system of discharge. This implies the arrival of medication ingredient(s) from a controlled discharge tranquilize conveyance framework continues at a rate that isn't just unsurprising dynamically yet in addition reproducible starting with one unit then onto the next. As it were, the framework endeavors to control medicate fixation in the objective tissue.

Hypertension (HTN or HT), otherwise called hypertension (HBP), is a long haul restorative condition in which the pulse in the supply routes is diligently lifted. Hypertension more often than not does not cause indications. Long haul hypertension³, be that as it may, is a noteworthy hazard factor for coronary vein malady, stroke, heart disappointment, fringe vascular ailment, vision misfortune, & ceaseless kidney infection. Hypertension is delegated either essential (fundamental) hypertension or auxiliary hypertension. Around 90–95% of cases are essential, characterized as hypertension because of nonspecific way of life & hereditary variables. Way of life factors that expansion the hazard incorporate abundance salt, overabundance body weight, smoking, & liquor. The rest of the 5–10% of cases are sorted as auxiliary hypertension, characterized as hypertension because of an identifiable reason, for

example, constant kidney ailment, narrowing of the kidney courses,.

Molecular structure of Isradipine

Isradipine has a place with the dihydropyridine (DHP) class of calcium channel blockers (CCBs), the most generally utilized class of CCBs. There are no less than five unique sorts of calcium directs in Homo sapiens: L-, N-, P/Q-, R- & T-type. CCBs target L-type calcium channels, the significant direct in muscle cells that intervenes compression. Like other DHP CCBs, isradipine ties specifically to dormant calcium channels settling their inert compliance. Since blood vessel smooth muscle depolarizations are longer in length than cardiovascular muscle depolarizations, latent diverts are more common in smooth muscle cells. Elective grafting of the alpha-1 subunit of the channel gives isradipine extra blood vessel selectivity.^{4,5,6}

The Isradipine Ethosomal development can deliver the drug molecules into & in the skin. This research finding revealed that CEG is a highly efficacious formulation. The method of Touitou *et al.*, was adopted with slightly modifications for preparing various formulations of Ethosomal constituting varied ethanol concentrations (20%- to 50%) by the technique of Sonication. The prepared Ethosomes were found to be discrete & spherical in shape^{7,8,9}. The transdermal application of Isradipine Ethosomal as a tremendous potential for commercial exploitation in the form of a patent. The research findings will further serve as standards for the Indian Pharma industry to scale up & develop a highly therapeutically efficacious Isradipine Ethosomal formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

Isradipine was a gift sample from MSN lab Hyderabad, **lecithin, ethanol and Propylene glycol** procured from Hetero Lab India, cholesterol was obtained from Granules India Hyderabad

Methods:

Preparation of Sonicated Isradipine Ethosomes (by Cold method):

Making slight modification to the Touitou *et al* method Isradipine Ethosomes were prepared¹³. The Isradipine Ethosomal system comprised of 20-50% of

ethanol, 10% of propylene glycol, 2-5% of phospholipids, 0.005g of cholesterol & an aqueous part of 100% w/w. At room temperature, 0.025 g of Isradipine was added to ethanol in a covered vessel along with propylene glycol & dissolved by stirring it vigorously. At 300°C mixture was heated using separate vessel & then drop wise it was added to the mixture in the centre of the vessel by stirring it at 700 rpm for 5min in a vessel which was covered. Then by using extrusion 30 method or sonication 30 method the particle size of Ethosomal formulation was reduced to the desirable extent.^{10,11,12} At last the Ethosomal formulation was kept under refrigeration. The following process was used to prepare Ethosomes spontaneously.

Characterisation of ethosomal formulation:

Vesicle size and zeta potential. Dynamic light scattering technique was utilized to measure the particle size and zeta potential of the prepared vesicles using Zetatract (Microtrac Inc., York, PA). An aliquot from each formulation was taken, loaded into the sample chamber and measured. Measurement was done in triplicate for each formulation.

Entrapment efficiency. An aliquots from each formulation were placed in eppendorf tubes (n = 3) and subjected to centrifugation at 20000 rpm for 1 hat 4 °C using (Sigma Laboratory centrifuge, 3K30, Ostrode, Germany). The supernatant was separated, filtered and the amount of free drug was determined using UV spectrometer.

$$\%EE = \left[\frac{\text{Total amount of drug used} - \text{amount of free drug}}{\text{Total amount of drug used}} \right] \times 100$$

Skin permeation studies:

By the use of a pair of scissors Wistar rats hairs were cut short carefully (<2mm) & then by the use of a scalpel the abdominal skin & the underlying connective tissue was separated from each other. On aluminium foil the excised skin is kept & the removal of subcutaneous & adipose tissue was done, which acts like diffusion cell with an area of diffusion 1.0cm² & it has 10 ml effective permeation volume at 32±10 C. Temperature & PBS (10ml of pH 6.5) buffer. After placing the skin between compartment receptor & compartment donor, Ethosomal formulation of 1.0ml was applied on skin epidermis. About Samples of 0.5ml were withdrawn from the diffusion cell at various time intervals of about 1,2,4,8,12,16,20,24 hrs & the samples were assayed by HPLC method^{13,14}.

Stability study:

By storing the particles at 4± oC the determination of their stability was done. After duration of about 180 days the particle size, zeta potential & entrapment efficiency are estimated by the earlier described methods.

In-vitro release kinetics:

The dissolution pattern obtained for all the formulations were graphically plotted for the following parameters namely.

Zero order kinetics:

Zero request discharge will be anticipated by the accompanying mathematical statement:

$$A_t = A_0 - K_0t$$

Where, A_t = Drug discharge at time 't'

First order kinetics:

A_0 = Initial medication fixation.

Initially - request discharge could be anticipated by the accompanying comparison:

$$\text{Log } C = \text{log } C_0 - Kt / 2.303$$

Where,

C = Medication Amount stayed at 't' C_0 = Medication Initial measure.

t = time

A straight line is plotted when log aggregate of percent medication remaining is plotted against time. When Slant worth duplicated with 2.303, steady "K1" is obtained.

Higuchi's model:

Higuchi's equation for classical diffusion explains the matrix devices drug release pattern by diffusion:

$$Q = [DE / \tau (2A - EC_s) C_{st}]^{1/2}$$

Peppas's model/ Korsmeyer equation:

For the elucidation of Liposomal formulation drug release pattern & exponential comparison of drug discharge (Peppas's law comparison /Korsmeyer mathematical statement) is employed, which is used for the polymeric medication release pattern.

Where

M_t / M_∞ = the portion of medication discharged at 't'.

n = Type of diffusion identified with the instrument of discharge

K = Polymer /drug framework geometrical & structural Constant. This study has created that admission of sodium salt prompts a rise of systolic pulse in the test animals

INDUCTION OF HYPERTENSION IN NORMAL RATS, BY MPA & SYSTOLIC BP MEASUREMENT IN RATS:

Grouping of animals is done into 6 groups containing 6 animals in each, where group I is control & rest of the groups are induced with subcutaneous MPA 20mg/Kg for hypertension. Group II was designated has MPA control Group III was administered EF2 20mg/Kg. Group IV is treated with EF4 20mg/Kg. Group Vis treated with EF7 20mg/Kg . Group VI is treated FD (marketed drug) 20mg/Kg.

The systolic BPs were measured for all the groups initially, after 1hr, after 2 hr, after 4hr, after 6hr, after 10hr & after 12hr. these BP measurements have been compiled in a comprehensive comparative table which is presented below.^{15,16}

B. Sodium induced method:

Non obtrusive pulse mechanical assembly made by Bio-pack framework inc. Santabarbara, USA was used for estimation of BP of the considerable number of rats. To the restrainer holder in which the tail of the rat was protruding out, for the B.P estimation of rat's tail-cuff method was employed. Average of three consecutive readings was noted.

INDUCTION OF HYPERTENSION IN NORMAL RATS, BY MPA & SYSTOLIC BP MEASUREMENT IN RATS:

The study design consists of 6 groups consisting of 6 animals in each group where treatment of these groups is as follows. Control group (Group I) they are normal & in the other 5 group's hypertension were induced by subcutaneous injection of 20mg/Kg body weight. Group II was designated as MPA control, Group III is treated with EF2 20mg/Kg. Group IV is treated with EF4 20mg/Kg. Group V is treated with EF7 20mg/Kg. Group VI is treated with FD (marketed drug) 20mg/Kg body weight.

The systolic BPs were measured for all the groups initially, after 1hr, 2 hr, 4hr, 6hr, 10hr & 12hr. These BP measurements have been compiled in a comprehensive comparative table which is presented below.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Spectral analysis of Isradipine

Isradipine pure drug was scanned in methanol between 200 nm & 400 nm using ultraviolet spectrophotometer. Isradipine was identified by its light absorption pattern which follows the absorption of light in the range 230 to 360 nm & a maximum absorbance at about 242 nm. A broad shoulder at about 242 nm was also observed which confirm the Isradipine .The Isradipine spectrum gave a highest peak at 242 nm & same was selected for further evaluations.

Table 1: Standard curve of Isradipine

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
2	0.207
4	0.422
6	0.601
8	0.808
10	0.989

Fig.1: Calibration Curve of Isradipine in Methanol at 242nm

Fig.4: DSC of Pure drug and excipients

Table 3: Size distribution of Isradipine Ethosomal formulation EF2:

S.No.	Size range		Average size (d)	No. of vesicles (n*)	% no. of vesicles	N × d
	Eye piece micrometer	In micrometer				
1	0-1	0.00-3.33	1.665	45	30	74.925
2	1-2	3.33-6.66	4.995	63	42	314.685
3	2-3	6.66-9.99	8.325	27	18	224.775
4	3-4	9.99-13.32	11.655	12	8	139.86
5	4-5	13.32-16.65	14.985	03	2	44.955
				$S_n = 150$		$S_{nd} = 799.2$

Fig.5: Size distribution of Isradipine Ethosomal formulation EF2

SEM Results of different Isradipine ethosomal formulation

Table 4: Comparison of particle size distribution in unsonicated & Sonicated Ethosomes

S.No.	Ethanol concentration	Average size of vesicles (μm)	
		Ethosomal preparation with Sonication	Ethosomal preparation without Sonication
1	20%	3.904	6.549
2	30%	5.320	3.818
3	40%	5.790	3.720

Table 5: Composition of different Sonicated Isradipine Ethosomes & Liposomes

Ethosomal formulation	Lecithin (Soya lecithin %)	Ethanol (%)	Propylene glycol (%)	Drug(g)	Cholesterol(g)	Water
EF1	2	20	10	0.025	0.005	q.s
EF2	3	20	10	0.025	0.005	q.s
EF3	4	20	10	0.025	0.005	q.s
EF7 (Liposomes)	2	-	-	0.025	0.005	q.s

Table 6: Composition of different UnSonicated Isradipine Ethosomes & Liposomes

Ethosomal formulation	Lecithin (Soyalecithin %)	Ethanol (%)	Propylene glycol (%)	Drug(g)	Cholesterol (g)	Water
EF4	2	20	10	0.025	0.005	q.s
EF5	3	30	10	0.025	0.005	q.s
EF6	4	40	10	0.025	0.005	q.s
EF7(Liposomes)	2	-	-	0.025	0.005	q.s

Table 7: Composition of different Ethosomal Gel formulation

Gelformulation	IsradipineEthosomal suspension(ml)	Carbopol (%)	Triethanolamine (ml)	Phosphatebuffer (pH7.4)
*G-4	0.025g	1.5	0.5	q.s
G-3	20	2	0.5	q.s
G-2	20	1.5	0.5	q.s
G-1	20	1	0.5	q.s

Organoleptic Characteristics:	Color: golden yellow Greasiness: Non greasy Grittiness: Free from grittiness Ease of application: Easily/smoothly applied Skin irritation: No skin irritation
Washability:	Easily washable without leaving any Residue on the surface of the skin.
Spreadability:	6.4g.cm/sec

Table 8: Entrapment Efficiency

S.N O	Sample code	Concentration	Dilution factor	Amount of drug T = CXDF	Entrapped drug E=T-U	% Entrapped drug %E=E/T x100	
01	EF1	Total drug(T)	9.65	10	96.5	71.2	73.7
		Free drug (U)	2.53	10	25.3		
02	EF2	Total drug(T)	9.717	10	97.17	67.92	70.0
		Free drug (U)	2.92	10	29.2		
03	EF3	Total drug(T)	9.832	10	98.32	65.82	66.9
		Free drug (U)	3.25	10	32.5		
04	EF4	Total drug(T)	9.95	10	99.5	53.5	53.7
		Free drug (U)	4.6	10	46.0		
05	EF5	Total drug(T)	9.93	10	99.3	45.8	46.12
		Free drug (U)	5.35	10	53.5		
06	EF6	Total drug(T)	9.7	10	97.0	41.0	
		Free drug (U)	5.6	10	56.0		
07	LP	Total drug(T)	9.94	10	99.4		
		Free drug (U)	6.5	10	65.0		

Table 9: % Drug Release Profile for Isradipine EF7 Liposomes

S.No.	Time	Dilution factor	%Drug Release	%Unreleased
1	0	10	0	100
2	5	10	0.75	99.25
3	10	10	6.26	93.74
4	15	10	19.68	80.32
5	30	10	28.48	71.52
6	60	10	33.02	66.98
7	120	10	42.6	57.4
8	240	10	49.7	50.3
9	360	10	57.77	42.23
10	720	10	67.1	32.9
11	1440	10	72.44	27.56

Table 10: Loss in percentage drug content during stability studies

Formulation code	Drug content in %									
	Initial		After 2 weeks		After 4 weeks		After 6 weeks		After 8 weeks	
	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C
EF2	100	100	100	99.84	99.68	98.49	99.62	97.93	98.58	96.69
EF4	100	100	100	98.82	99.65	98.03	98.99	97.30	98.32	96.32
EF7 (Liposome)	100	100	100	98.54	99.48	97.30	99.12	97.23	98.25	96.13

Table 11: Decrease in entrapment efficiency during stability studies

Formulation code	Drug content in %									
	Initial		After 2 weeks		After 4 weeks		After 6 weeks		After 8 weeks	
	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C	4±2 ° C	27±2 ° C
EF2	77.30	77.54	75.56	73.24	73.59	72.30	72.46	70.94	69.32	68.30
EF4	64.30	64.57	62.67	61.23	62.36	60.51	60.96	58.30	60.73	56.30
EF7 (Liposome)	52.36	52.74	47.96	47.45	45.96	44.62	45.32	43.53	39.56	37.62

In-Vivo Results**Table 12: Bp Measurement by MPA Induced Hypertension Method:**

GROUP	TREATMENT	INITIAL	1 HOUR	2 HOUR	4 HOUR	6 HOUR	10 HOUR	12 HOUR
1	CONTROL	116.8 ± 4.57	114.9 ± 9.356	115.2 ± 6.45	113.2 ± 3.56	112.0 ± 4.98	113.97 ± 2.54	114.4 ± 3.64
2	MPA CONTROL	158.6 ± 1.65	159.6 ± 7.689	156.6 ± 5.78	157.8 ± 9.96	157.5 ± 6.43	155.9 ± 8.67	157.3 ± 7.63
3	EF2	157.9 ± 2.46	145.1 ± 5.78	133.6 ± 1.53	130.9 ± 6.96	122.9 ± 9.68	112.9 ± 1.613	105.65 ± 3.56
4	EF4	159.5 ± 2.467	152.6 ± 6.93	148.9 ± 6.15	141.3 ± 5.14	132.3 ± 6.41	127.6 ± 5.63	115.9 ± 2.546
5	EF7	156.6 ± 1.986	149.5 ± 0.59	141.4 ± 7.52	136.6 ± 6.36	131.7 ± 6.32	128.8 ± 6.39	122.2 ± 4.780
6	FD	156.6 ± 1.458	151.8 ± 0.356	147.5 ± 9.61	140.7 ± 4.81	132.8 ± 5.43	130.8 ± 8.65	124.3 ± 7.64

Table 13: BP Measurement by Sodium Induced Hypertension Method:

GROUP	TREATMENT	INITIAL	1 HOUR	2 HOUR	4 HOUR	6 HOUR	10 HOUR	12 HOUR
1	CONTROL	115.4 ± 3.56	114.9 ± 4.356	115.2 ± 6.45	114.5 ± 3.56	113.2 ± 6.45	113.9 ± 2.50	114.5 ± 3.64
2	MPA CONTROL	156.6 ± 5.75	157.8 ± 9.90	154.5 ± 5.75	156.6 ± 5.55	156.6 ± 5.53	154.5 ± 5.55	156.6 ± 7.60
3	EF2	152.5 ± 2.46	143.2 ± 5.75	130.7 ± 1.95	125.5 ± 2.25	120.7 ± 3.47	110.8 ± 8.89	101.4 ± 4.11
4	EF4	155.9 ± 3.11	150.3 ± 3.49	145.6 ± 6.66	140.4 ± 3.99	135.8 ± 5.99	125.6 ± 7.18	118.6 ± 4.18
5	EF7	156.3 ± 3.47	155.2 ± 8.86	154.1 ± 4.52	150.3 ± 9.17	148.1 ± 2.22	145.5 ± 4.44	140.9 ± 3.38
6	FD	156.1 ± 2.11	155.96 ± 9.95	154.8 ± 3.51	152.3 ± 5.14	150.5 ± 5.97	149.8 ± 4.33	146.7 ± 7.12

FTIR Analysis of Isradipine

FTIR Analysis of Pure Isradipine drug and excipient does not show any significant interaction

DSC Study

DSC spectrums it is observed that there is a minor change in the melting point energies of pure drug, polymers than in the optimized formulation which are negligible

ETHOSMES WITH SONICATION:

Sonication strategy was received to diminish the vesicular size by giving abnormal state vitality to the lipid suspension. The kind of Sonicator utilized was test Sonicator keeping in mind the end goal to create high vitality to a little aliquot of the lipid suspension. The chose Ethosomal definitions were subjected to Sonication by the test Sonicator. The photomicrograph uncovered lessen the molecule size of the Ethosomes subsequent to being subjected Sonication. The aftereffect of size and shape uncovered consistency with the perceptions of Jain NK et al

ETHOSMES WITHOUT SONICATION:

Ethosomes were readied including the equation containing 2-5% Phospholipids, 20-40% ethanol and amount adequate water were found to show up as multilamellar vesicles. It was watched that the Ethosomal lamellae were equally divided deeply. This affirms the vesicular structure of high ethanolic fixation were available.

This Liposomal definition was seen to be longer than that of Ethosomal detailing which were portray to be multilamellar and picked up type as well.

Estimate dispersion and normal vesicular size investigation were done according to the system specified under procedure

Vesicular size Distribution

The outcomes acquired by vesicular size examination indicated convergence of ethanol influence vesicular size. The measure of Ethosomes diminished as the grouping of ethanol expanded with the biggest vesicles estimate $6.549 \mu\text{m}$ containing 20% ethanol & smallest $3.720 \mu\text{m}$ containing 40% ethanol

Since the sizes of vesicles are lessened by Sonication, mic already to locate the size dispersion may not be attractive. Consequently unique programming created by "BIOVIS" was utilized to locate the best possible vesicular size dissemination of the Sonicated items Result acquired here demonstrated the most extreme vesicular size is $6.549 \mu\text{m}$ for formulation containing 20% ethanol (EF4) & minimum is $3.720 \mu\text{m}$ for

formulation containing 40% ethanol (EF6). Results obtained here are in same relation with concentration of ethanol^{17,18}.

In vivo study

A profound investigation of the information acquired from the in-vivo discharge ponders by the two strategies to be specific the MPA incited hypertension and the sodium prompted hypertension techniques, the BP estimation examines have uncovered that the EF2 plan was the best when contrasted with EF4, EF7 and FD (advertised medication) detailing of Isradipine. These discoveries set up that EF2 (Sonicated Ethosomal plan) inspired the best helpful action of lessening the systolic circulatory strain of the male Wistar pale skinned person rats. Subsequently it can be reasoned that Sonicated Ethosomes of Isradipine which have been planned by the creator are very viable for the treatment of congestive heart disappointment (CHF), hypertension, tachycardia and these are deserving of being protected^{19,20}

CONCLUSIONS:

In light of the in-vitro total %drug discharge near investigations of Isradipine details it was built up that EF2 (Sonicated Ethosomes) discharged greatest medication of 93.7%, EF3 (Sonicated Ethosomes) 89.3%, EF1 (Sonicated Ethosomes) 88.4%, EF4 (Unsonicated Ethosomes) 87.11%, EF5(Unsonicated Ethosomes) 78.2%, EF6 (Unsonicated Ethosomes) 75.5%, EF gel 74.35%, liposome's 72.44% trailed by showcased medicate FD 47.26%.EF2 was pronounced the best in view of in-vitro % sedate discharge parameter which was right around two times the advertised medication

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